

Dependence of statistical results on definitions and extents of study area: examples from cirques and glaciers

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Abstract— The boundaries of geographic study areas are mostly defined at an early stage of research, and rarely investigated further. Yet statistical results are critically dependent on the extent of the study area and the way in which its boundaries are defined. The dilemma is that a small study area may lack the number of features required for significant results, whereas a large study area may include sub-areas with different relationships between variables, so that the averaged values or trends obscure relationships. Results for regional trends and mean azimuths of aspect are especially likely to be affected. Examples here are from mountain glaciation (cirques and glaciers), but the conclusions apply to many fields of physical geography and earth science.

I INTRODUCTION

The advancement of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and the availability of high-resolution satellite imagery and digital elevation models (DEM) enable the analyses of a large population of geographic data for regional and global trends. However, such analysis may be affected by the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP), which has been discussed extensively by human geographers and cartographers (Openshaw and Taylor, 1981; Evans, 1981; Goodchild, 2011). Many MAUP-related studies concern the cases for which data are available or analysed, for example, the data collected for various administrative areal divisions. In comparison, few studies have been investigated similar issues in physical geography. Dark and Bram (2007) considered MAUP in physical geography, mainly in relation to scale effects in remote sensing (pixels) and in drainage tracing on DEMs (grid mesh) – both involving equal units. The impacts of data aggregation to varied

shapes and sizes of geographic areas are seldom investigated. Here, we use three examples to demonstrate the impacts of analysing trends and directions in cirque datasets for different extents of investigated area. We suggest that results vary with the size, shape and uniformity of study area.

II EXAMPLE 1: GLACIATION OF THE CENTRAL HIMALAYAS

Empty cirques were measured in an area of 224 x 134 km between 79.6 and 82.1°E and 29.8 and 30.9°N in central Himalayas (Fig.1, best enlarged; Li et al., 2023). This is a large and diverse area, with enough cirques to give highly significant statistical results. The cirques (Fig. 1) are in groups with different climates: the Nanda Devi, Byasrikh and Saipal Himal are exposed to the monsoon from the south, while the Gurla Mandhata (Naimon'anyi) and Chandi Himal mountains are in their rain shadow and therefore much drier and with a higher snowline, past and present. We first test the impact of data aggregation in different spatial divisions on regional easting and northing trends in cirque floor altitudes, then biases in cirque aspect (local asymmetry of glaciation). Both have been used to make inferences about former climates.

The regressions in Table 1 show the relationship between cirque floor altitudes and UTM east and north coordinates (in km). Such trends are used to infer former glacier ELA trends related to precipitation and temperature. The data obey assumptions about uniform distribution of deviations. The regional trend across the central Himalayas is strong, rising mainly northward but also eastward. For the whole study area the rise is at 14 m/km toward an azimuth of 020°, compatible with the 5.8 mm/km decline in precipitation toward 038° (from 1 km resolution data in WorldClim v2.1).

We made a twofold split around approximately 81.2°E, through the pass at Baling La: this would be a West-East split except that in the south six cirques just west of this are closer to cirques in, and therefore are allocated to, the East region, so the terms Northwest and Southeast are used. This confirms the northward rise, especially in Southeast (from Saipal Himal to Chandi Himal). The eastward rise, however, is confined to Northwest.

Fig. 1. The central Himalayas study area. Empty cirques are blue polygons.

TABLE 1. TWO-CONTROL REGRESSIONS PREDICTING CIRQUE FLOOR ALTITUDE (m) from UTM coordinates (in km) for the whole C. Himalayas area, for a twofold division into regions, and for the six subdivisions. The east and north coefficients give component gradients in m/km. $p = 0.0868$ for Nanda Devi, 0.0000 for all others.

area	east	north	R^2 (%)	rmse (m)	n
C. Himalayas	4.743	13.179	46.7	287	455
<i>Regions</i>					
Northwest	6.410	14.315	30.6	273	173
Southeast	-1.955	16.851	65.8	241	282
<i>Subdivisions</i>					
1. Nanda Devi	6.479	7.030	9.7	408	32
2. Panch Chuli	12.698	28.023	55.6	229	86
3. Gunji	15.956	19.771	42.1	156	55
4. Saipal Himal	0.106	17.045	26.7	98	98
5. G. Mandhata	-6.871	20.096	84.6	146	100
6. Chandi Him.	4.343	18.748	52.8	207	84

The cirques cluster in separate mountain ranges and further subdivisions can be made to define more compact, uniform areas separated by valleys and passes. The Northwest region is elongated and oriented WNW-ESE: it can be further split into three subsections by UTM eastings 336 km and 395 km. The westmost is dominated by Nanda Devi, although the empty cirques are on lower peripheral mountains. The central subsection includes Panch Chuli. The eastern is around Gunji, from UTM 395 km to 463 km and north of 3350 km. Regional trends for these three consistently show a northward rise greater than an eastward: floors are higher toward north of northeast. Two are highly significant with R^2 of 42% and 56%, but the Nanda Devi

subsection has only 32 empty cirques, giving completely insignificant results.

The Southeast region divides naturally into three blocks or massifs. The eastmost is Chandi Himal, straddling the Nepal – Tibet border east of Labtse La: the north slope is the source of the Brahmaputra R. (Trak Tsangpo, Yarlung Tsangpo). Immediately west is Gurla Mandhata (Naimon'anyi), east of the town of Purang in Tibet but extending into Nepal. South of that, across the Changla La, is Saipal Himal with Jethi Bahurani, mainly in Nepal. The regressions are highly significant, with R^2 between 27% and 85%. In all three subsections the northing coefficient is consistently strong, while the easting coefficient varies from negative to positive. This is where the monsoon rain shadow effect is strongest, with higher cirque floors in the dry north. All trends are more northward than those in the Northwest region. The regional trends in cirque floor altitudes confirm that precipitation providing snowfall came from the south, in the past as today.

Results for cirque aspect are used to infer the relative importance of shade, wind and other effects, moderated by topographic trends. For Central Himalayas these are less interesting. For the whole study area, vector mean aspect is 038.5° and strength is 7.5%, but $p = 0.075$ (using Rayleigh's test for unimodal bias) and the 95% confidence limits are estimated as 341° to 096°, disappointingly broad. The two regions give consistent means (033.3° and 044.2°) but contrasting strengths (13.3% and 4.0%). Subsections have varied mean aspects of 000°, 168°, 003°, 010°, 095° and 055°. It seems that the degree of symmetry is sufficiently high that this further subdivision produces capricious results, with local topography more effective than slope climates. The Gunji subsection, however, has a due north mean with a strength of 33.8%.

In summary, the C. Himalayas cirque aspect distribution is symmetrical, with a weak tendency to favour northeast aspects in the Northwest region. This is somewhat different to that of the 1535 modern glaciers, downloaded from Randolph Glacier Inventory 6.0., with a vector mean of 017.8° and strength 24.2%. The 1175 glaciers smaller than 1 km² likewise have mean 013.3°, strength 21.8%. Compared with 038.5 for cirques, there is a (weak) hint of greater influence from westerly winds in the past.

III EXAMPLE 2: GLACIATION OF THE EASTERN TIAN SHAN.

The E. Tian Shan study area (also from Li et al., 2023) extends over 134 km north-south and 302 km east-west, between 83.7-87.5°E and 42.9-44.2°N (Fig. 2). As it is clearly in the west-wind belt, with precipitation from the west, we expect cirque floors and modern glacier ELAs to rise eastward as precipitation declines. This decline, calculated from estimates of precipitation at roughly 1 km resolution from WorldClim v.2.1, is however at only 0.2 mm/km: much less than the 5.8 mm/km northward decline in the C. Himalayas. The decline is toward 100°, i.e. close to eastward as expected. Median altitudes of modern glaciers rise at 1.0 m/km toward 065°.

Cirque floor altitudes, however, rise southward: at 2.5 m/km toward 182° (Table 2). As the study area is elongated east-west, an initial threefold division into West, Centre and East is used. Significant results are produced in each region, with declines more northward than eastward in Centre and East. In West, however, floor altitudes decline westward as expected and the northward coefficient is insignificant.

Fig. 2. E. Tian Shan cirques: blue: empty cirques; green: subdivisions. (Best enlarged)

As each of these regions was split by major valleys, and by a central area with large glaciers where cirques could not be measured, a further division into six subdivisions was defined, each having a more compact cluster of cirques. The results (Table 2) are varied. The Northwest and South-central subdivisions show no significant trends: in fact, the R^2 values are negligible, even negative after adjustment for the degrees of freedom lost, and the $rmse$ are close to the standard deviations of floor lowest altitudes. The other four subdivisions show northward declines (southward rises), much steeper than for the whole study area. It is to be expected that small areas show steeper trends: in fact, the steepest is for Northeast, a small cluster of 24 cirques. In each the eastward decline is much less than the northward, and in Southwest it is reversed and insignificant.

TABLE 2. ANALYSES OF CIRQUE FLOOR ALTITUDE trends for the whole E. Tian Shan area, for three regions and for six subdivisions. Cirque floor altitude (m) is regressed on UTM eastings and northings (km): east and north coefficients are in m/km. Coefficients statistically insignificant at the 0.05 level are left blank.

area	east	north	R^2 (%)	$rmse$	p	n
E. Tian Shan		-2.517	10.5	220	0.0000	675
<i>Regions</i>						
West	1.550		1.9	202	0.0139	343
Centre	-3.087	-5.399	29.4	236	0.0000	137
East	-2.258	-7.230	27.3	186	0.0000	195
<i>Subdivisions</i>						
1. Northwest			0.0	233	0.8035	146
2. Southwest		-4.300	8.7	169	0.0001	188
3. N-central	-6.788	-16.014	30.3	234	0.0000	63
4. S-central			0.0	230	0.6360	78
5. Northeast	-13.787	-44.087	25.9	192	0.0165	24
6. Southeast	-2.391	-10.272	26.2	180	0.0000	176

In this case the more detailed division does not explain the lack of an eastward rise in cirque floor altitudes to match the reduced precipitation. It does, however, confirm the robustness of a southward rise. Although not apparent in the modern precipitation, the implication is that around the maxima of past glaciations precipitation (snow) was brought from more northerly sources than today: the plains of Xinjiang

to the south were the more arid then as now. The situation is complicated by the numerous cirques filled by modern glaciers, as these could not be measured.

The steepest trend component is the northward decline of 44 m/km over 22 km in Northeast. This, however, is not supported by the regression of cirque floor altitudes on northing alone, which is insignificant. We conclude that, despite the p value of 0.0165, the set of 24 cirques is too small to support a two-control regression. The 95% confidence interval on the -44 m/km gradient is from -73 to -15 m/km. On the other hand, the sets of 137 and 195 cirques in Centre and East sections, similarly tested, show a robust northward decline, as does the E. Tian Shan study area as a whole.

The favoured direction in which glacial cirques face has also been used as evidence of palaeoclimate (Mîndrescu et al., 2010). The E. Tian Shan is in an arid, sunny region, so glaciers are likely to form and survive more on north-facing than on south-facing slopes. The WNW-ESE orientation of the whole area, and of most component mountain ranges (Fig. 2), militates against east- and west-facing cirques. The vector mean of the 675 empty cirques is 019.5°, north-northeast, which suggests a dominant shade effect moderated by some morning-afternoon differences, probably in cloudiness. Division into three regions shows some reduction in the eastward component in the West and the East regions, but an insignificant ($p = 0.129$) directional bias in the 137 cirques of the Central section.

The six-fold subdivision shows significant results only in two subdivisions, Southwest and Southeast, with greater vector strengths (22 and 28%) and a dominantly northward tendency (Table 3). For North-central $p = 0.066$ and 95% confidence limits are 352 and 094°. The other three subsections give completely insignificant results, to the extent that confidence limits cannot be calculated for Northwest and Northeast. Again there may be problems from exclusion of glacier-filled cirques.

TABLE 3. VECTOR ANALYSES OF CIRQUE ASPECTS in E. Tian Shan. Only significant results are shown: all p values are 0.000.

Area	Mean (°)	Strength (%)	Number	95% conf. (°)
E. Tian Shan	019.5	14	675	358-041
W. region	010.2	15	343	341-039
E. region	008.5	22	195	342-034
Southwest	002.7	28	188	341-024
Southeast	013.2	22	176	346-041

Assuming that almost all the 2997 modern glaciers have sources in cirques, the glacier mean aspect of 356.9° with a strength of 52.7% would shift the overall mean for cirques very close to north (taking only the 2677 glaciers smaller than 1 km², the mean of 355.1° and strength of 53.0% produce the same result). The conclusion is that, like modern glaciers, the glaciers that eroded E. Tian Shan cirques faced north, uninfluenced by wind or by morning: afternoon asymmetry.

IV EXAMPLE 3: CIRQUES OF THE ENGLISH LAKE DISTRICT.

Cirque aspects for the whole Lake District massif (Fig. 3) show a clear climatic signal, with shade favouring poleward aspects, and shelter from westerly winds favouring eastward (Evans and Cox, 1995). Results for 8 individual mountain ranges, separated by passes, show considerable variation (Table 4). The numbers of cirques in each are

small, but this is not a random variation: it shows the effects of topographic lineation. The Western Fells are oriented east-west, with few possible east-facing sites: shade gives a north-facing dominance. The Central Fells, Coniston – Black Combe and the Eastern Fells (Helvellyn – Fairfield range) are elongated north-south, favouring east-facing cirque sites and providing few suitable north-facing sites: shelter from westerly winds encouraged glacier formation on east-facing sites. The Far Eastern Fells (High Street range) have north-south and east-west ridges: they and the compact Sca Fell – Bow Fell massif come closest to the overall Lake District cirque vector mean. The Northwestern Fells are oriented northwest-southeast and give a NNE vector mean. The 95% confidence limits on vector means vary between $\pm 15^\circ$ and $\pm 34^\circ$ for the divisions, in comparison to $\pm 10^\circ$ for the whole Lake District.

Implications of numbers of cases are even greater for correlations between morphometric variables. Whereas for the whole District all correlations of ± 0.16 or stronger are significant at the $p = 0.05$ level, the number of significant correlations within each division is greatly reduced by the small numbers. For the two areas with 10 cirques each, correlations need to be over ± 0.64 ; for that with 33 cirques, ± 0.35 .

The eight mountain ranges are too small to define trends in floor altitude. Even for the whole Lake District, spatial trends are weak.

Fig.3. Cirques of the English Lake District, with contours at 457 and 610 m. Green lines follow valleys and passes to divide the District into 8 mountain ranges, named in Table 4.

TABLE 4. VECTOR MEAN AND STRENGTH OF HEADWALL ASPECTS in divisions (mountain ranges) of the English Lake District, ordered by vector mean. All have Rayleigh's $p < 0.001$ except for Central, where $p = 0.001$.

Name (range)	Mean (°)	Strength (%)	Number
Western	015.3	62.2	33
Northwestern	022.8	76.2	16
Northern	036.4	82.1	10
Sca Fell-Bow Fell	048.7	59.0	18
Far Eastern	055.2	69.0	25
Eastern	063.1	59.0	32
Coniston-Black Combe	087.7	83.9	14
Central	102.8	64.9	10
LAKE DISTRICT TOTAL	049.3	60.2	158

V DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

The regional trends for subdivisions, as well as for a complete study area, are varied and can be inconsistent. Analyses of subdivisions help test the robustness of generalizations and identify which subdivisions dominate the overall statistical results. For correlations, datasets here smaller than 25 tend to give excessively broad confidence intervals: more than 50 is desirable and 100 – 200 can give significant correlations for the weakest correlations likely to be of interest. For larger datasets the homogeneity of the study area should be considered.

The regional trends derived from small areas can give misleading results. With large areas, analysing subdivisions tests the robustness of overall trends. The possibility of non-linear trends should be investigated although high-order polynomials are likely to be unstable and certainly should not be extrapolated. For directional statistics, as for cirque and glacier aspects, small datasets can give significant results if asymmetry is strong (i.e. high vector strengths, high consistency). These results may, however, relate to either topography or climate. High strengths can be produced if one side of a mountain range is studied, but that is of no climatic significance. If a drainage basin is analysed there will be a bias to the direction of the trunk stream. For datasets with more symmetry, mean directions may vary capriciously.

Evans (2012) considered the importance of mountain ranges (as opposed to drainage basins or geometric outlines) as relevant study areas with meaningful boundaries. Compactness (spatial proximity), however, is also important for climatic interpretations: clustering needs to be respected and isolated cirques or glaciers should be allocated to the nearest cluster, i.e. compactness of study areas is important, as well as size and uniformity. Here we advocate multi-scale analysis in terms of study areas. Results can vary considerably even between adjacent areas. Analysis of nested study areas complicates interpretation; but it can increase confidence in results that are resilient.

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